

Part of
DMP for Public funding and party organizational development
in Latvia and Estonia

Description

LCS FARP

Description

The data capture donations to Latvian political parties between 2015 and 2024.

Researchers

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Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

LU

Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data are provided by the Anti-Corruption Bureau of Latvia (KNAB). The data will be analyzed to discern trends in party financing, dynamics of the size of donations, timing of donations etc. This will help understand the role of public finance in the funding of political organizations.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

12

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The data provided by KNAB are publicly available data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers, journalists, political party officials.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

March 2026.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Univeristy of Latvia repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The data is to be available freely.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-04-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jānis Ikstens (0000-0003-3191-6305)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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